

Dendrome

Forest Tree Genome Research Updates

Dendrome
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April 1996

Volume 3, Number 1

Molecular Genetics at the Forest Research Station of INRA Cestas France

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photo of *Fagus sylvatica* L. var *tortuosa* Pépin
in Forest of Verzy, France
photographer: Gérard Hammalian

The laboratory of forest genetics and tree improvement of INRA Cestas is conducting research in molecular genetics in two different fields: (1) population and evolutionary genetics in temperate European oaks and tropical trees and (2) genome analysis and marker-assisted selection in maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*) and Eucalypts (*E. grandis* and *E. urophylla*). In total, 6 scientists and 6 Ph.D. students are involved in these projects which are supported by different grants from INRA, the French Ministries of Research and Agriculture and the European Union. One project aims at studying the genetic, molecular and physiological determinants of water-use efficiency and drought resistance in major forest trees. The other project aims at drawing synthetic maps of gene diversity and provenance performance for utilization and conservation of oak genetic resources in Europe.

Population and evolutionary genetics in European temperate oaks and tropical trees

Investigations are focusing on *Q. petraea* and *Q. robur* which are two widespread species growing throughout Europe from Spain to Russia and represent the largest economic resources among European broadleaf species. Activities aim at the description of gene diversity of nuclear and cytoplasmic markers at different hierarchical and spatial levels (species, region, population) with particular emphasis on the mechanisms involved in the dynamics and evolution of genetic diversity including anthropomorphic factors. Different topics within this general framework required the development of molecular markers adapted to the field of interest.

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cooperative efforts with colleagues who have already collected the samples, mostly in Germany, Italy and in the Netherlands. Data relative to oak deposits will be extracted from the data base in order to construct isopollen maps for a series of ten-time slices since 15000 BP. Since chloroplasts are only maternally inherited in oaks as shown by segregation analysis in controlled crosses, the comparison of the geographic map based on cpDNA with the isopollen maps will allow retracing the post glacial migration routes and to depict refugial areas.

Comparison of provenance performance and cpDNA

All provenance tests that were established in the different countries will be measured and the data of the provenances will be compared to their cpDNA cytotype. Any difference in growth, form or adaptive traits, that is due to the maternal evolutionary origin (glacial refugia) will be identified by the comparison of phenotypic variation and cpDNA polymorphism.

Assessments of levels of diversity in natural stands

In addition to the cpDNA survey, nuclear diversity will be assessed in reference populations in the 8 countries. A reference population is a population sampled with the same criteria throughout the natural distribution and consists of at least 200 mature trees. These analyses are restricted to *Q. petraea* and *Q. robur*, the two most widespread species in Europe. Microsatellites will be used to assess allelic richness and diversity. For the time being three microsatellite loci are scored with PCR techniques and silver staining, exhibiting from 16 to 26 alleles in a population. The results will be delivered in the form of geographic maps of (1) patches of cpDNA haplotypes, (2) isopollen lines of oak fossil pollen deposits, and (3) contours of provenance performances. Additional maps will be created by combining the information, as putative postglacial migration routes and location of glacial refugia. All data will be made available to the scientific community in the form of a data base where cpDNA data, pollen data and provenance results will be stored. The maps that will be constructed will be considered as references not only for population biologists and geneticists but also for foresters. They will be of crucial utility for identifying material of unknown origin and for defining seed transfer rules.

Some Results of the Experiments on a Mutagenesis of Forest Plants

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Experiments on mutagenesis of *Pinus silvestris* L. were initiated 1979 by Professor P.I. Molotkov in the laboratory of forest selection of the Ukrainian Research Institute of Forestry and Agricultural Afforestation. The influence of gamma-rays, beta-rays and seven chemical mutagens solutions on seeds, sprout seeds, grafts, ovaries, and shoots of growing pines has been studied. In addition, the influence of the chemical mutagens solutions on seeds of 23 varieties and species (*Picea*, *Pinus*, *Juniperus*, *Thuja*, *Platycladus*, *Chamaecyparis*, *Ginkgo*, *Sorghum*, *Amaranthus*, *Weigela*, etc.) has been studied at the Botanical Gardens of Kharkov State University. Chemical mutagenesis appears to be a reliable method for the stimulation of seedling growth and diversity. Several ornamental varieties have been selected. Some of them have been stabilized as interesting ornamental plants (varieties albo-variegata, aureo-variegata, aureo-marginata, aurea media picta, inversa, compacta, etc.). We have now multiplied the best of them and have them available for distribution.

Forest Genetics Program Expanding at the University of British Columbia

With three new forest genetics faculty members in the Department of Forest Sciences at the University of British Columbia in 1996, the Forest Genetics program at UBC is growing rapidly. Joining Forest Sciences Department Head Gene Namkoong and molecular forest geneticist John Carlson are Kermit Ritland (currently in the Botany Department, University of Toronto), Sally Aitken (Forest Science Department, Oregon State University) and Yousry El-Kassaby (Pacific Forest Products). Kermit Ritland and Sally Aitken will hold, respectively, the NSERC/Industrial Research Senior and Junior Chairs in Genetics. Yousry El-Kassaby, Director of Applied Forest Research at Pacific Forest Products, has joined the faculty on a part-time basis. The Forestry Sciences Centre, scheduled for completion in 1998, will provide new research facilities for population, quantitative, conservation and molecular genetics research.